

Integration of Gamified Instruction on Students' Academic Performance

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ABSTRACT

Several factors can significantly impact students' academic performance, among these is disengagement during lessons and this stands out as a prominent concern. This lack of engagement can have a far-reaching effect on students' academic achievement, primarily manifesting lower scores and reduced learning outcomes. The primary objective of this study is to investigate the impact of incorporating gamified instructions into traditional classroom lessons. By introducing game elements and mechanics into the learning environment, the study aims to evaluate how this approach influences motivation, engagement and academic performance. The researcher utilized a quasi-experimental design, which involves establishing a cause-and-effect relationship between the variables in controlled setting. This type of design allows the investigation of the impact of a certain variable on outcomes. The research employed a quantitative design, utilizing two Grade 7 classes, each with 25 participants, to assess the effects of the gamified approach using the ClassPoint application. Statistical analyses, including paired sample t-tests and two-sample t-tests, revealed a significant improvement in competency levels, indicating the efficacy of gamification in enhancing learning outcomes. The positive aspects included a fun learning experience, increased motivation, heightened engagement, and enhanced learning. To sum it up, this study systematically investigated the impact of integrating gamified instructions on the academic performance of Grade 7 students in Araling Panlipunan. The findings illuminate a positive trend, indicating that the gamified approach significantly enhances students' competency levels compared to traditional methods. The gamified instruction, implemented through the ClassPoint application, facilitated a more enjoyable learning experience, increased motivation, and heightened engagement. The statistical analyses, employing paired sample t-tests and two-sample t-tests, underscored the effectiveness of gamified instruction in improving academic outcomes.

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INTRODUCTION

Gamification has garnered significant attention in educational literature due to its potential to enhance engagement and learning outcomes among students. Recent studies delve into various aspects of gamification, shedding light on its multifaceted impact on education. A study by Xu et al. (2021) explores the role of gamification in improving students' intrinsic motivation and academic performance. The findings suggest a positive correlation between well-designed gamified elements and increased student engagement, leading to higher achievement levels.

Moreover, the work of Rodriguez et al. (2022) investigate the influence of gamification on collaborative learning environments. The study reveals that gamified approaches contribute to fostering teamwork, communication, and critical thinking skills, indicating a broader spectrum of benefits beyond individual academic performance.

According to studies, gamification has a significant impact on motivation and engagement, such as in the study conducted by Kijpoonphol & Phumchanin (2018). In which it was reflected in their study that the experimental group with gamified application exhibited a higher level of performance compared to the control group. Another study conducted by Ozturk & Korkmaz (2020), entitled “The Effect of Gamification on Students’ Academic Achievements in Social Studies Course, Attitude towards the Course and Cooperative Learning Skills”, in which, their research findings indicate that integration of gamification activities into the learning process positively influenced students’ academic achievements.

Over the years, several gamified applications have resurfaced and made their impact to education. The incorporation of this information communication technology (ICT) in teaching-learning practices has become an essential component in the 21st century era (Abdelrady & Akram, 2022). Technology-integrated modes of instruction not only bring innovativeness to pedagogical approach, but also help learners’ cognitive abilities flourish, strengthen satisfaction and foster engagement. It is found out in the study of Ghavifekr and Rosdy (2015) that teaching and learning with technology is more effective than the traditional classroom setup with board and chalk. Likewise, the ClassPoint application is the pedagogical instrument that will be used in this study. According to Lugatoc (2022), ClassPoint is an interactive tool that is embedded with Power Point presentations. Students can follow along on their devices, and the teachers can get students’ response synchronously during the class. A teacher can add any interactive activities offered by the application to any existing or newly created PowerPoint file (Abdelrady & Akram, 2022). In relation to prior studies, Bong and Chatterjee (2021) identified the relation of ClassPoint-integrated instruction methods in enhancing students’ engagement.

With ClassPoint, the delivery of quiz questions can be done without using another application during the session. It has several modes of questions, including multiple-choice questions, short questions, quick poll, word cloud, short answer, slide drawing and image upload. In addition, ClassPoint has features that make teachers annotate the presentation as the teacher presents the lesson. Students only need their phones to join the collaborative activities by just logging into <http://classpoint.app>, then enter the class code and create a username that would be used throughout the lesson (Lugatoc, 2022). Through the powerful features offered

by ClassPoint and the likes, the positive literature review that this context has garnered, and the society's natural love for games are the motivations that fuel the researcher to explore.

Despite the numerous positive impacts of gamification, its utilization remains limited. The contextual gap in research on gamification in Baybay National High School pertains to lack of specific studies investigating the implementation and impact of gamified instruction in this said institution. Although there may be studies on gamification in education in other institutions, the unique factors present in Baybay National High School, are technological resources, specific challenges, school culture, students' characteristics and readiness. Therefore, conducting research that specifically targets these factors in the school would provide valuable insights into the feasibility and potential benefits of gamification in this particular setting. Similar research in this context in the future could explore the experiences of teachers and students, regarding integration of gamification. It would also be beneficial to investigate the necessary adaptations and considerations required for successful implementation of gamification in Baybay National High School.

In summary, closing this contextual gap in gamification research at Baybay National High School, offers multiple advantages of bestowing contribution to existing literature and providing practical insights for educators. Furthermore, the impact of this paper extends beyond Baybay National High School, as the data gathered by this study can be a valuable resource for similar studies hereafter.

The significance of this study lies in its potential to revolutionize education and learning outcomes within the context. The potential to influence teachers and administrators to embrace the utilization of gamification in the classroom is a huge leap in the institution. The shift of mindset among administrators and facilitators, would grandly improve students' motivation and engagement. Research on gamification in Baybay National High School can shed a light to integrate gamification in many other teaching strategies. By exploring the integration of gamification to other instructional strategies, teachers can synthesize an effective gamification technique to further enhance classroom engagement and performance. This knowledge can support the continuous improvement of teaching practices and professional growth.

Overall, the study of gamification in the institution grasps as it provides valuable and targeted insights into how this approach impacts motivation, engagement, academic performance and teaching practices within the school. Additionally, this study offers practical and specific knowledge that can guide educators and policymakers in enhancing learning experiences in Baybay National High School and beyond. Finally, the result of this study can inform administrators, facilitators and stakeholders that the implementation of effective gamification strategies can lead to increased students' engagement and overall success.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the effect of integrating gamified instruction on students' academic performance in *Araling Panlipunan 7*. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions.

1. What is the performance level of the respondents in *Araling Panlipunan 7* before the integration of gamified instructions on the following competencies?

- 1.1. *Konsepto ng Asya tungo sa paghahating heograpiko*
- 1.2. *Ugnayan ng tao at kapaligiran*
2. What is the performance level of the respondents in *Araling Panlipunan 7* after the integration of gamified instructions on the following competencies?
 - 2.1. *Konsepto ng Asya tungo sa paghahating heograpiko*
 - 2.2. *Ugnayan ng tao at kapaligiran*
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of performance between the traditional group and the gamified group before and after the integration of gamified instructions?
4. What are the benefits and challenges of a gamified instruction on students?
5. What can be proposed based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher utilized a quasi-experimental design, which involves establishing a cause-and-effect relationship between the variables in controlled setting. This type of design allows the investigation of the impact of a certain variable on outcomes. By using this design, the researcher compared the outcomes of the experimental group (gamified instruction), with those of the control group (traditional instruction). This allowed for the researcher to gather data of the casual relationship between the intervention and the observed outcomes.

The Sample and Locale of the Study

The sample for this study consisted of Grade 7 students. The researcher chose two classes as the sample due to potential funding limitations. For this investigation, the researcher applied a sampling strategy known as purposeful sampling. Purposeful sampling involves selecting participants based on predetermined criteria that align with the study's aims and needs. This sampling strategy allowed the selection of individuals who met the necessary criteria or had relevant experiences related to the study question.

The criteria for selecting the sample included evaluating the strength of signal/internet in the classroom, the presence of students with electronic devices, and students' academic performance prior to admission to Grade 7.

Purposive sampling referred to a group of non-probability sampling techniques in which units were selected because they had characteristics needed in a sample. This sampling method relied on the researcher's judgment when identifying and selecting the individuals, cases, or events that could provide the best information to achieve the study's objectives. It was particularly useful if the researcher needed to find information-rich cases or make the most out of limited resources (Nikolopoulou, 2022).

By employing purposive sampling, the researcher meticulously chose participants possessing specific features or attributes crucial for a comprehensive evaluation of the gamified instruction's impact on academic performance. The sample comprised two Grade 7 classes, each section consisting of 25 students as participants. The distinctive aspect of this study involved the strategic switching of roles between the control group and experimental group.

This design ensured that both groups experienced both the traditional and gamified instructional approaches, eliminating potential biases or perceptions of favoritism. Each section had an equal opportunity to benefit from different teaching methods, contributing to the study's data reliability and avoiding any unintended disparities between the groups.

Baybay National High School served as the institution of learning where the research was conducted and set as the study's location. The perfect setting for carrying out the debut of gamified instruction in the Araling Panlipunan topic for Grade 7 students was the said school. The research was done in educational settings, such as classrooms and other appropriate learning situations. The study took place at Baybay National High School because the researcher was a current faculty member there. This option made it simple to communicate with the school administration and collaborate with them, which made it easier to carry out the study. The study's overall quality was improved by doing the research in an environment the researcher was already familiar with and where they had access to the resources and student population. It was crucial to remember that the results might only apply to Baybay National High School and might not have a direct bearing on other educational institutions.

Research Instrument

This study consisted of two parts. Part one was used for the pretest and posttest of the experiment. This section of the study addressed the objectives related to the first, second, and third research questions, providing insights and answers to these specific inquiries. Furthermore, the credibility and reliability of the pretest and posttest questions were highly robust as they were taken from the official modules of *Araling Panlipunan* provided by the Department of Education. Intentionally, in accordance with the layout of the modules provided by the Department of Education, which consisted of a pretest and posttest with fifteen questions, this study administered fifteen questions in both the pretest and posttest.

Though, minor adjustments were made to some of the questions to guarantee their relevance and applicability while still adhering to the study's objectives.

Consequently, students' academic performance was measured using both ordinal and ratio scaling. The scoring criteria were as follows, in alignment with DepEd Memorandum No. 158, S. 2011. These scoring categories were used to answer this paper's objectives one, two, and three.

Beginning	74% and below
Developing	75%-79%
Approaching Proficiency	80%-84%
Proficient	85%-89%
Advance	90% and above

The second phase of the study, the focus shifted towards a comprehensive exploration of the benefits and challenges encountered during the implementation of the experiment. To

gather insights, a survey checklist instrument was meticulously crafted. Drawing insights from existing literature on gamification in education and aligning with the specific objectives of the study, the researcher collaborated with colleagues to devise a checklist. This instrument was strategically crafted to encompass a diverse range of student experiences, ensuring a comprehensive exploration of the impact of gamified instruction on various aspects of the learning process. The checklist included items related to perceived benefits, such as increased motivation, enhanced engagement, and a fun learning experience. Simultaneously, it probed into the challenges faced by students, encompassing aspects like access to gadgets, internet connectivity issues, and competitive pressures. This instrument was designed to provide a holistic understanding of the gamified learning experience, shedding light on both positive and challenging aspects faced by students during the intervention. To achieve this, a survey checklist was administered to the participating students. To enhance the validity and reliability of the survey checklist, a rigorous validation process was undertaken. The checklist was presented to the *Araling Panlipunan* Department's ICT coordinator for thorough evaluation and feedback. By leveraging the expertise of the school's ICT coordinator, the checklist underwent a thorough review to assess its appropriateness, clarity, and alignment with the study's objectives. Their valuable insights ensured that the checklist effectively captured the intended benefits and challenges related to gamified instruction, enhancing its validity and relevance to the research goals.

In compliance with legal guidelines pertaining to the reproduction of instrument materials, the researcher ensured that the study adhered to the prescribed protocols. Specifically, the study aligned with the Intellectual Property Code or RA 8293, section 176, which stated that government works in the Philippines were not subject to copyright protection. However, prior approval from the government agency or office responsible for creating the work was required for commercial exploitation. As this study was conducted for non-profit purposes, no further authorization was necessary for utilizing the content from the official *Araling Panlipunan 7* modules. Furthermore, section 185 of the Intellectual Property Code acknowledged that the fair use of copyrighted materials for educational and research purposes was not considered infringement.

Data Gathering and Analysis

To gather the data, approval to conduct the study was sought first from the Dean's Office of the Graduate School. A consent letter was sent to the SDS and the School Principal, requesting permission to conduct the study at Baybay National High School. A letter was also sent to the parents or guardians of the respondents, which requested permission to allow their child to be a part of the study and data gathering.

Prior to the commencement of the instructional lesson, respondents were administered pretest questionnaires. These questionnaires had been sourced directly from the module developed by the Department of Education and thoroughly evaluated by DepEd officials. As a result, the reliability of these questionnaires was considered highly robust.

In this study, the gamified application ClassPoint was utilized as part of the gamified instruction. Class activities had game-elements added using this application. It offered features such as leaderboards, badges, and a reward system that could be used to monitor students' development, recognize their accomplishments, and offer rewards for active engagement. The incorporation of ClassPoint into the educational activities enabled the students to have a dynamic and engaging learning experience. It offered quick feedback, promoted constructive rivalry, and built a sense of accomplishment, resulting in a more interesting and enjoyable learning environment.

During the first week, the researcher focused on teaching the competency "*Konsepto ng Asya Tungo sa Paghahating Heograpiko*" using a pretest to assess the students' prior knowledge. Following this, the researcher delivered the lesson using a traditional approach for Section A and a gamified approach in Section B. The gamified approach included leaderboards, badges, and a reward system during the implementation, and this was done using the powerful application ClassPoint. At the end of the lesson, the posttest examination was administered to evaluate the students' learning outcomes. To prevent potential memorization of answers, the posttest questions mirrored the pretest questions. However, to ensure fairness and accuracy, the question items were randomized and rearranged. This approach-maintained consistency in assessing the students' knowledge while minimizing the risk of answer recall from the pretest to the posttest.

Moving on to the second week, the researcher addressed the second competency, "*Ugnayan ng Tao at Kapaligiran.*" In this week, Section A and Section B switched roles, with Section A experiencing the gamified approach and Section B following the traditional approach. The decision to switch the roles between the two classes, with one experiencing the gamified approach and the other the conventional teaching approach, was made to avoid any potential perception of favoritism or unfair treatment. This approach ensured that both sections had an equal opportunity to benefit from different instructional methods and eliminated any potential disadvantages that could arise from solely using the conventional teaching approach. By implementing this switching of roles, the study aimed to maintain ethical standards and provide equitable learning experiences for all students involved.

Subsequently, to measure the academic performance level of the class before the integration of gamified instruction, a pretest was administered. The scores obtained from the pretest underwent descriptive statistical analysis, specifically calculating the mean of the class scores. This statistical analysis provided insights into the average performance level of the students before the implementation of gamified instruction. Similarly, to measure the students' academic performance after the integration of gamified instruction, a posttest exam was administered. The scores obtained from the posttest underwent the same procedure of descriptive analysis, including calculating the mean score of the class. This analysis enabled the teacher to evaluate the students' performance level following the integration of gamified instruction. These scores are transmuted based on the 60% passing rate guidelines.

Beginning	8.74 and below
Developing	8.75 – 9.75
Approaching Proficiency	9.76 – 11.00
Proficient	11.01 – 12.25
Advance	12.26 and above

To assess whether there existed a distinction in performance between gamification and traditional instructional approaches, the study conducted inferential analyses employing two statistical methods: the two-sample t-test and the paired sample t-test. The two-sample t-test was utilized to compare the gamified group with the traditional group, enabling an exploration of significant differences in their performance. This statistical tool is apt for determining whether the means of two independent groups are significantly different from each other.

Concurrently, the paired sample t-test was employed to scrutinize changes in performance within groups over time. Specifically, it compared the pretest and posttest scores within each group. This test is suitable for analyzing the means of two related groups, making it an effective tool to discern if there were significant improvements or deteriorations within the same group after the intervention.

The rationale behind using these statistical procedures lies in their ability to provide insights into the effectiveness of gamified instruction compared to traditional methods. The two-sample t-test aids in ascertaining if there is a general performance distinction between two distinct instructional approaches. On the other hand, the paired sample t-test allows an in-depth investigation into the specific impact of gamified instructions by assessing changes in performance within the same group. Together, these tests contribute to a comprehensive evaluation of which instructional method yielded superior outcomes.

The evaluation of the integration of gamified instructions involved a checklist capturing key aspects, revealing significant positive and negative dimensions. Notably, participants overwhelmingly reported a fun experience (88%) and increased motivation (62%), demonstrating the engaging nature of gamified learning. Enhanced engagement (56%), improved learning (52%), and instant feedback (24%) were also acknowledged, emphasizing the multifaceted benefits of this instructional approach. However, challenges included slow internet connectivity (48%), gadget unavailability (34%), perceived excessive competitiveness (34%), limited internet data (22%), and laggy phone issues (14%). These findings underscore the need for addressing technical and access-related challenges to optimize the effectiveness of gamified instruction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Performance Level of the Participants Before the Integration of Instruction

At the beginning of the academic year, the researcher promptly launched the study, which aimed to investigate the influence of integrating gamification on students' academic performance. What was particularly striking was the initial performance of both classes, Gamified Group and the Traditional Group, in the pretest phase. As expected, these assessments revealed lower academic results, aligning with the baseline expectations for a pretest. What is particularly intriguing is the remarkable similarity in the mean scores of both classes during this pretest phase.

This shared baseline performance established a robust starting point for evaluating the effects of gamification on academic performance in a comparative context. It enabled the researcher to closely monitor and analyze how each class progresses differently throughout the study. This convergence in pretest scores offered valuable insights into the initial academic standing of the two groups and sets the stage for a comprehensive assessment of the impact of gamified instruction over time.

Table 1. Distribution of Data Before the Integration of Gamified Instructions

Group	Competency	n	Total Scores	Mean	s.d.	Performance Level (D.O. 158 S. 2011)
Gamified	Asya Tungo sa	25	108	4.32	1.35	Beginning
Traditional	Paghahating Heograpiko	25	119	4.76	1.59	Beginning
Gamified	Ugnayan ng	25	178	7.12	2.07	Beginning
Traditional	Tao at Kapaligiran	25	182	7.28	2.32	Beginning

The table presents the descriptive statistics for the competency scores of the Gamified and Traditional groups across two domains: "*Asya Tungo sa Paghahating Heograpiko*" and "*Ugnayan ng Tao at Kapaligiran*." The mean scores, standard deviations, and performance levels are outlined.

In terms of "*Asya Tungo sa Paghahating Heograpiko*," both the Gamified and Traditional groups exhibit mean scores indicative of the "Beginning" performance level, with the Gamified group scoring slightly lower (4.32) compared to the Traditional group (4.76). This suggests that, on average, both groups are at the initial stages of proficiency in this

competency. The standard deviations in both groups indicate a moderate level of variability among individual scores.

Moving to the competency "*Ugnayan ng Tao at Kapaligiran*," interestingly, both groups again show mean scores corresponding to the "Beginning" performance level, with the Gamified group scoring 7.12 and the Traditional group scoring 7.28.

The results suggest that, in the context of the studied competencies, there is no substantial difference in the performance levels between the Gamified and Traditional instructional approaches. Both groups fall within the "Beginning" level, indicating that the integration of gamification did not yield a significant advantage in these particular competencies. The comparable mean scores in both competencies suggest that, initially, there was no difference in the performance levels between the Gamified and Traditional groups. This indicates that, before the intervention, both groups were at a similar proficiency level.

Research conducted by Bai et al. (2020) underscore that the influence of gamification on academic performance is intricately tied to the thoughtful design of gamified elements, levels of student engagement, and the alignment of gamification strategies with specific learning objectives. This emphasizes the critical need for a meticulous approach to implementing gamification successfully, taking into account various instructional factors.

Building on this, literature, including studies by Khan (2019), affirms the potential of gamification to positively impact student engagement and motivation, subsequently influencing academic performance. These findings stress the significance of scrutinizing the intricate dynamics between gamification strategies and specific competencies. Educators are encouraged to refine gamified elements deliberately to achieve optimal impact.

Difference of Performance Level Between the Gamified and Traditional Group

The utilization of a paired sample t-test serves as a sturdy statistical approach to gauge the significance of interventions within both classes. This analytical method is particularly effective in discerning the relative impact of each intervention, thereby providing insights into which approach yielded more statistically significant results. By comparing the pretest and posttest scores within each group, the paired sample t-test enables a precise evaluation of the effectiveness of the interventions employed in both the Gamified and Traditional groups.

This method allows for a thorough examination of the extent of change within each group and enables a direct comparison between gamified instruction and traditional methods, revealing their distinct impacts on academic performance. This sturdy statistical analysis enhances the study's credibility, providing valuable comprehension into instructional strategies and their effects on academic outcomes.

Table 2. Paired Sample T-Test – Gamified Group

Asya Tungo sa Paghahating Heograpiko	N	Mean	T calculated	Df	t critical	Significance
Pretest	25	4.32				
Posttest	25	12.2	20.74	24	1.711	Significant
Ugnayan ng Tao at Kapitaligiran						
Pretest	25	7.12				
Posttest	25	12.12	9.51	24	1.711	Significant

Table 3. Paired Sample T-Test – Traditional Group

Asya Tungo sa Paghahating Heograpiko	N	Mean	T calculated	Df	t critical	Significance
Pretest	25	4.76				
Posttest	25	9.44	10.15	24	1.711	Significant
Ugnayan ng Tao at Kapitaligiran						
Pretest	25	7.28				
Posttest	25	10.24	6.34	24	1.711	Significant

The paired sample t-tests conducted on both the Gamified and Traditional groups reveal compelling insights into the effectiveness of instructional interventions in enhancing students' competencies in two distinct areas: "*Asya Tungo sa Paghahating Heograpiko*" and "*Ugnayan ng Tao at Kapitaligiran*."

In the Gamified Group, the pretest-posttest analysis for "*Asya Tungo sa Paghahating Heograpiko*" yielded a substantial increase in mean scores from 4.32 to 12.2. The calculated t-value of 20.74 (df = 24) far exceeds the critical t-value of 1.711, indicating a highly significant difference. This implies that the gamified instructional approach significantly enhanced students' understanding of the geographical division of Asia. Similarly, in the domain of "*Ugnayan ng Tao at Kapitaligiran*," the gamified group demonstrated a noteworthy improvement from a mean pretest score of 7.12 to a posttest mean of 12.12. The calculated t-value of 9.51 (df = 24) is significant, indicating a substantial impact on comprehending the relationship between humans and their environment.

In contrast, the Traditional Group also exhibited significant improvements. In "*Asya Tungo sa Paghahating Heograpiko*," mean scores increased from 4.76 to 9.44, with a calculated t-value of 10.15 ($df = 24$), surpassing the critical t-value. This denotes a highly significant difference, emphasizing the effectiveness of the traditional instructional method in enhancing geographical understanding. Likewise, in "*Ugnayan ng Tao at Kapaligiran*," the traditional group demonstrated a noteworthy improvement from a mean pretest score of 7.28 to a posttest mean of 10.24. The calculated t-value of 6.34 ($df = 24$) is highly significant, indicating a substantial impact on understanding the relationship between humans and their environment.

Implications of these findings underscore the versatility of both instructional methods in fostering student learning. The gamified approach, characterized by elements of play and interactivity, proved to be more effective as the traditional method. Educators can consider incorporating gamified elements into their teaching strategies, recognizing the potential for heightened student engagement and improved outcomes. Furthermore, these results advocate for a diversified instructional approach, allowing educators to tailor methods based on specific competencies and learning objectives. As the educational landscape evolves, understanding the impacts of different instructional strategies becomes paramount for fostering effective and engaging learning environments.

Two-Sample T-Test

At this juncture, the posttest results of both classes were subjected to a detailed comparative analysis. The main objective was to determine which instructional method, gamified or traditional, had a more pronounced impact on students' academic scores. This comparative analysis sought to elucidate the effectiveness of the two teaching approaches in terms of enhancing students' academic performance.

By examining thoroughly and comparing the posttest outcomes, the researcher aimed to draw meaningful conclusions regarding the relative advantages of gamified instruction and traditional teaching. This analysis provides a critical basis for assessing the study's central research question: whether the integration of gamification significantly influences students' academic achievements.

Moreover, the data of the comparison offer insights into the potential benefits of incorporating gamified elements into the educational process. The findings can guide educators and instructional designers in making informed decisions about the adoption of innovative teaching methods to optimize students' learning experiences and outcomes.

Table 4. Two-Sample T-Test (Concept 1 – Asya Tungo sa Paghahating Heograpiko)

Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	Two-Sample T-Test	
					t Critical	t Calculated (two-tailed)
Gamified	25	12.20	1.55	48	2.011	4.58
Traditional	25	9.44	2.58			

Table 5. Two-Sample T-Test (Concept 2 – Ugnayan ng Tao at Kapaligiran)

Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	Two-Sample T-Test	
					t Critical	t Calculated (two-tailed)
Gamified	25	12.12	2.39	48	2.011	2.58
Traditional	25	10.24	2.76			

Based on the comparison of the calculated t-value with the critical t-value, the study affirms that a significant difference is present between the impacts of gamification and the traditional approach. This evidence supports the effectiveness of gamification over the traditional method.

Analyzing the results as presented in Table 4.1 and Table 4.2, it became increasingly evident to the researcher that the integration of gamified instruction was indeed more effective compared to the traditional teaching method.

This realization, drawn from the cumulative data and performance trends, reinforced the notion that gamification holds significant promise for enhancing the academic performance of students. The consistency of these findings across multiple weeks of the study emphasizes the robustness of the gamified approach.

Benefits and Challenges of Integration of Gamified Instruction

Throughout the study, the integration of gamified instruction offered various benefits and also presented some challenges. Here is the discussion of the key benefits and challenges identified in the study.

Table 5. Benefits and Challenges of Integration of Gamified Instructions

Benefits	N	Frequenc y	Percentag e	Challenges	N	Frequenc y	Percentag e
Fun	5	44	88%	Slow	5	24	48%
Experience	0			Internet	0		

Increase Motivation	5	31	62%	No Gadget	5	17	34%
	0				0		
Increase Engagement	5	28	56%	Too Competitive	5	17	34%
	0				0		
Enhance Learning	5	26	52%	No Internet Data	5	11	22%
	0				0		
Instant Feedback	5	12	24%	Laggy Phone	5	7	14%
	0				0		

Table 5 provides a comprehensive overview of the benefits and challenges associated with the integration of gamified instructions in the educational setting. The data clearly indicates that the gamified approach is overwhelmingly associated with a fun experience, as evidenced by the high frequency count of 88%. This fun experience, in turn, contributes significantly to increased student motivation and engagement, with respective frequency counts of 62% and 56%. The positive impact extends further to enhancing learning, as reported by 52% of the participants.

Despite these favorable outcomes, it is crucial to note the challenges identified in the data. Slow internet emerges as a substantial obstacle, capturing the highest frequency count at 48%. This limitation significantly impacts the frequency of instant feedback, which records the lowest count at 24%. The challenges posed by slow internet connectivity directly impede the instantaneous feedback mechanism intended by gamified instructions. This juxtaposition of high benefits and challenges underscores the need for strategies to address technical constraints, ensuring the seamless and effective implementation of gamified instructional methods. In essence, while the gamified approach proves highly advantageous, the efficacy hinges on mitigating challenges such as internet speed to fully harness its potential in enhancing the learning experience.

In the rapidly evolving landscape of educational technology, scholars have emphasized the imperative of inclusivity and accessibility. Bell et al. (2023) contribute to this discourse by underlining the significance of designing educational technology that considers diverse levels of internet access. As internet connectivity remains a variable factor globally, especially in educational contexts, their insights underscore the necessity for solutions that are adaptive to varying technological infrastructures. Complementing this perspective, Boyle et al. (2022) delve into the nuanced relationship between device performance and user experience. Their findings emphasize the critical role of addressing technical challenges for the seamless integration and success of gamified interventions. The study highlights that beyond conceptual design, the tangible aspects of technology, such as device functionality, significantly influence the overall user experience.

Furthermore, May's (2021) work directs attention to broader societal implications. Beyond the immediate technical challenges, he underscores the need for policies and interventions that actively work towards bridging digital divides in education. The digital divide, encompassing issues of access, skills, and usage, has profound implications for the equitable implementation of educational technologies. May's insights reinforce the idea that while technological innovations like gamification hold great promise, they must be embedded in a broader framework that considers socio-economic disparities and ensures that the benefits are accessible to all learners, irrespective of their digital contexts. Together, these studies contribute to a holistic understanding of the challenges and considerations in implementing educational technologies like gamification in diverse educational settings.

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

This study delved into the impact of integrating gamified instructions on the academic performance of Grade 7 students in Araling Panlipunan. The research employed a quantitative design, utilizing two Grade 7 classes, each with 25 participants, to assess the effects of the gamified approach using the ClassPoint application. Statistical analyses, including paired sample t-tests and two-sample t-tests, revealed a significant improvement in competency levels, indicating the efficacy of gamification in enhancing learning outcomes. The positive aspects included a fun learning experience, increased motivation, heightened engagement, and enhanced learning. However, challenges such as slow internet, gadget unavailability, competitiveness, and technical issues were identified.

The study underscores the need for strategic interventions to address challenges and optimize the benefits of gamified instruction. Recommendations include designing programs considering varying internet access levels, policies to bridge digital divides, and refining gamified elements for maximum impact. As the study contributes valuable insights to the discourse on instructional strategies, it offers practical guidance for educators and policymakers in leveraging gamification effectively in diverse educational settings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study systematically investigated the impact of integrating gamified instructions on the academic performance of Grade 7 students in Araling Panlipunan. The findings illuminate a positive trend, indicating that the gamified approach significantly enhances students' competency levels compared to traditional methods. The gamified instruction, implemented through the ClassPoint application, facilitated a more enjoyable learning experience, increased motivation, and heightened engagement. The statistical analyses, employing paired sample t-tests and two-sample t-tests, underscored the effectiveness of gamified instruction in improving academic outcomes.

However, the study also unveiled challenges, primarily related to technical issues and access barriers. Slow internet connectivity and gadget unavailability emerged as significant

hurdles, emphasizing the need for strategic interventions to ensure equitable access to gamified learning. The insights gained from this research contribute to the broader discourse on instructional strategies, emphasizing the importance of refining gamified elements for optimal impact, addressing technical challenges, and promoting inclusive education. As educational technologies continue to evolve, this study provides practical recommendations for educators and policymakers to harness the benefits of gamification while navigating its associated challenges.

Recommendations

In response to the findings and challenges identified in this study, a proposed gamification program is designed to optimize the benefits while mitigating the challenges. The program aims to create a dynamic and engaging learning environment tailored to the specific needs of the students. To address the issue of slow internet, a hybrid model is suggested, incorporating both online and offline gamified elements. This approach ensures that even in situations with connectivity limitations, students can seamlessly transition between online and offline components.

The program includes a diversified set of gamified modules catering to different learning preferences. These modules not only offer a fun experience but also integrate various forms of instant feedback, promoting a continuous feedback loop between students and educators. Recognizing the significance of device performance, the program encourages students to use a range of devices, ensuring compatibility and performance optimization.

To motivate and sustain engagement, a reward system is proposed, where students earn points or badges for completing tasks and achieving learning milestones. The program also incorporates collaborative gamified activities, fostering a sense of healthy competition and teamwork. Regular assessments will be embedded within the gamified structure to gauge the effectiveness of the intervention continually. Moreover, to enhance accessibility and bridge digital divides, a comprehensive digital literacy component is integrated. This component provides guidance on navigating digital platforms, troubleshooting common technical issues, and maximizing the learning experience in various technological contexts. In essence, the proposed gamification program is tailored to be flexible, adaptive, and inclusive, offering a holistic approach to address both the benefits and challenges identified in the study.

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